

VALKYRIES

D6.4 VALKYRIES **harmonisations on first aid** **preparedness and cross-sectorial** **collaboration**

Reference Number: D6.4

Ed/Rev: A/0

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Date: 31/03/2023

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101020676

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Document Changes Record

Edit./Rev.	Date	Chapters	Reason for change
A/0	31/03/2023	All	Original Document

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable D6.4 aims: (1) To analyse the compliance of System Requirements defined in D2.7 with the VALKYRIES objectives and achieved results described in WP6 deliverables; (2) Based on the commonly agreed upon among the leaders of WP4, WP5, and WP6 methodology, to analyse the Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats of each prioritized harmonisation opportunity; (3) To present in details the VALKYRIES approach for implementation of the suggested opportunity; (4) To formulate some suggestions and recommendations regarding the process of harmonisation of first aid preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration in case of cross-border Multi-Casualty Incident (MCI).

(Common points through deliverables of WP4, WP5 and WP6)

Due to the horizontality of the project at this stage and the similarities in work packages 4, 5 and 6 a common work methodology has been established for them. This allows to inter-compare results between work packages, to be efficient and to provide a holistic result.

For these reasons a common TOC has been established for deliverables D4.4, D5.4 and D6.4. Some chapters are common to these deliverables, which is why they are marked in their title as (common).

2. Identification

Deliverable Title: VALKYRIES harmonisations on first aid preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration

Deliverable Id: D6.4

Deliverable Title Abbreviation: D6.4

Name of lead participant: BDI

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Type: Report (R)

Dissemination Level: Public (PU)

Proposed Classification Level: Non-Restricted

Reporting Conditions: Funding Requirement (FR)

Linked project Work Package: WP6

Linked project tasks: T6.1, T6.2, T6.3, T6.4, T6.5

Action: Study

Status: First Release

Document Layout: Custom layout

Details: This specification applies to the project VALKYRIES: Harmonization and Pre-Standardization of Equipment, Training and Tactical Coordinated procedures for First Aid Vehicles deployment on European multi-victim Disasters funded under the SU-DRS03-2018-2019-2020 (IA), subtopic 3 Grant Agreement of the Horizon 2020 (H2020) tendering conditions. This document presents the selected enablers for addressing the requirements of the reference integration and reports the application of the VALKYRIES harmonisation methodology on them.

3. Introduction

The goal of this deliverable is to analyse the top-5 ranked collaboration, education and training harmonisation opportunities in WP6 with respect to the importance and feasibility to suggest these opportunities for harmonisation at the EU level. To achieve this goal, the WP6 team analysed first the compliance of System Requirements defined in D2.7 with the VALKYRIES objectives and achieved results described in the WP6 deliverables. Besides, based on the commonly agreed upon among the leaders of WP4, WP5 and WP6 methodology, the partners carried out a SWOT analysis to identify the Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats of each prioritised harmonization opportunity. Moreover, the VALKYRIES approach for implementation of each of the suggested opportunities is presented in detail. Finally, some suggestions and recommendations regarding the process of harmonisation of first aid preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration in case of cross-border Multi-Casualty Incidents (MCI) are formulated.

3.1. Objective (common WP4, WP5, WP6)

The primary objective of the VALKYRIES project is to develop, implement, validate, and apply innovative theoretical foundations, methods, prototypes and their demonstration on a reference integration for supporting the ongoing/planned European actions for pre-standardisation and harmonisation technologies, procedures, preparedness and cross-sector/border cooperation for first aid response at disaster management by emergency health services, with the focus on their vehicular deployments.

To achieve this primary objective and address the challenges identified above, VALKYRIES establishes 9 specific and measurable objectives that are introduced below:

- **VALK-OBJ-1 (Map of growing commercial and R&D opportunities):** Analyse the existing/ongoing technological, procedural, education and collaborative opportunities of the first aid response supplier markets and related signs of progress beyond the state-of-the-art able to improve the EU disaster resiliency.
- **VALK-OBJ-2 (Sustainable Regulation and ethical compliance):** Analyse the first aid response cross-sector, cross-border, and cross-hierarchy regulatory and ethical principles, identifying minimum standard requirements, lacunae and hurdles, and developing recommendations to policymakers and stakeholders to facilitate their enforcement through the consolidation of a harmonised regulatory framework and the implementation of new strategic schemes.
- **VALK-OBJ-3 (Sustainable Pre-standardisation and Standardisation):** Research and analyse the pre-standardisation opportunities concerning the first aid response enablers, resulting in recommendations, common requirements, guidelines, and enforcement tools towards constituting a novel and sustainable reference model, being implemented at new standardisation actions.
- **VALK-OBJ-4 (Sustainable certification and conformity assessment criteria):** Analyse the accreditation and certification opportunities concerning the first aid response enablers, including the enforced conformity assessment criteria, evaluation procedures and facilities; resulting in recommendations, guidelines, and strategies to prompt sustainable certification, accreditation, and homogeneity assessment.

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- **VALK-OBJ-5 (Sustainable Harmonisation framework):** Development of a holistic framework for supporting the standardisation/harmonisation of first aid response enablers assuming their cross-sector, cross-border, and cross-hierarchy hybrid dimensions, bearing in mind the vertical/horizontal propagation of consequences of the decisions made between technical, procedural and collaborative domains.
 - **VALK-OBJ-6 (Harmonisation of vehicular first aid technologies, procedures, and collaboration):** Research, analyse and apply the VALKYRIES' recommendations, guidelines and harmonisation tactics on reference equipment, technologies, procedures, preparedness, raise awareness and related collaborative solutions.
 - **VALK-OBJ-7 (Cross-sectorial collaboration, civilian protection, volunteering, and military assistance):** Research, analyse and expand the harmonisation framework towards facilitating, guiding, and enhancing the cooperation between vehicular first aid responders with other disaster management actors, among them firefighters, law enforcement agencies, civilian protection, military or heterogeneous volunteering.
 - **VALK-OBJ-8 (Reference integration and interoperation):** Reference integration and interoperation of the harmonised technological, procedural and collaborative solutions based on the common requirements and gap mitigations prioritised by the committed end-users and practitioners.
 - **VALK-OBJ-9 (Large EU scale cross-border demonstrations):** Evaluation and demonstration of the interoperability and enhancements derived from harmonising vehicular first aid related enablers at four cross-border and cross-sectorial scenarios: Spain-Portugal, Slovakia-Austria, Bulgaria-Greece, and Norway-Netherlands.

For the scope of deliverable D6.4, to develop an EU-wide roadmap for the standardisation of collaboration, education and training capabilities for first aid response in MCI, VALKYRIES researchers defined several requirements related to the various specific objectives of the Project in D2.7 (Definition of System Requirements and Demonstration Use Cases).

There are 2 types of requirements regarding WP6 deliverables:

- **Base requirements:** requirements extracted from the description of the tasks in the DoW (technical proposal) of the Valkyries Project. They are considered mandatory.
- **Common requirements:** are those requirements that are not explicitly described in the DoW (therefore considered as extended requirements) but are adopted by agreement between the Project partners. They are optional requirements.

VALKYRIES adopts the following requirements prioritisation scale:

- **P1 (Highest Priority):** Priority requirements that must be met for the system not to fail. They will be partially covered by functionalities that will be verified in the previous verification and validation processes. The fulfilment of the requirement may condition the progress towards the fulfilment of the P2 priority conditions.
- **P2 (Moderate priority):** P2 requirements must be fulfilled once P1 requirements have been satisfied. The requirements will be partially covered by functionalities that will be verified in the intermediate verification and validation processes.
- **N/A (Not Applicable):** The requirement shall be considered from the very beginning (by design).

3.1.1. Verification and Validation

The methods to use for verification and validation of the requirements are Demonstration, Analysis, Test, Inspection and Special Qualification Methods (any other verification procedure).

3.1.2. Expert consultation

The results of the harmonisation and pre-standardisation tasks have been subjected to internal validation processes with the most expert project researchers in each case, consultation with the External Advisory Board (EAB) and, in some cases, external validation with experts from outside the Project.

3.2. Requirements compliance matrix

Description of the requirements can be consulted in D2.7 – Definition of System Requirements and Demonstration Use Cases document. Table below presents the WP6 Traceability Matrix.

ID	Priority	Traceability with objectives	WBS Deliverables	Compliance	Results
REQ_BASE_T6.1_1	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D6.1/D6.5 D6.2/D6.6 D6.3 D6.4 D2.8	REQUIRED	INSPECTION Emerging collaboration opportunities, gaps and roadmaps are presented in D6.6, D6.3 and D6.4.
REQ_BASE_T6.1_2	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D6.4 D2.8 D7.3	REQUIRED	DEMONSTRATION The proposed architecture (D2.8) enables the use of resource federation.
REQ_BASE_T6.1_3	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D6.1/D6.5 D6.2/D6.6 D6.3 D6.4 D7.3	REQUIRED	DEMONSTRATION The use of a framework capable of managing multi-domain data will be demonstrated in D7.3.
REQ_COM_T6.1_1	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D6.1/D6.5 D6.2/D6.6 D6.3 D6.4	REQUIRED	INSPECTION The proposed architecture (D2.8) enables the use of resource federation.

ID	Priority	Traceability with objectives	WBS Deliverables	Compliance	Results
REQ_COM_T6.1_2	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D2.8 D6.1/D6.5 D6.2/D6.6 D7.3	RECOMMENDED	DEMONSTRATION The use of Single Sign-On to log the system will be demonstrated in D7.3.
REQ_COM_T6.1_3	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D2.8 D6.1/D6.5 D6.2/D6.6 D6.3 D6.4	REQUIRED	INSPECTION The definition and deployment of trust domains will be done in D7.3.
REQ_COM_T6.1_4	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D2.8 D6.3 D6.4	REQUIRED	INSPECTION The unification of method for data-exchange in cross-border domains will be analysed in D4.3 and D4.4.
REQ_COM_T6.1_5	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-2 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-8 VALK-OBJ-9	D2.8 D6.1/D6.5 D6.2/D6.6 D6.3 D6.4 D7.3	REQUIRED	DEMONSTRATION The use of secure and trusted environments to communicate actors using the platform will be demonstrated in D7.3.
REQ_BASE_T6.2_1	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-9	D6.1 / D6.5 D6.2 / D6.6 D6.3 D6.4	REQUIRED	INSPECTION The information is presented in D6.6, D6.3 and D6.4 submitted documents.
REQ_BASE_T6.2_2	P1	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-9	D6.1 / D6.5 D6.2 / D6.6 D6.3 D6.4	REQUIRED	INSPECTION The information is presented in D6.5, D6.6, D6.3 and D6.4 submitted documents.

ID	Priority	Traceability with objectives	WBS Deliverables	Compliance	Results
REQ_BASE_T6.2_3	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-9	D6.4	RECOMMENDED	INSPECTION The education and training kit is presented in this document.
REQ_BASE_T6.2_4	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-3 VALK-OBJ-4 VALK-OBJ-5 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-9	D6.4	REQUIRED	INSPECTION/TEST The proposed recommendations will be tested during use cases demonstrations and reported in D7.7 document (M24)
REQ_COM_T6.2_1	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-7	D6.3 D6.4	REQUIRED	INSPECTION The needed knowledge and skills for first aid responders are described in this deliverable. They are basis for the developed education and training kit for first responders.
REQ_COM_T6.2_2	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-7	D6.3 D6.4	REQUIRED	INSPECTION The results from the study of education and training (E&T) programmes for first responders at the EU level and the programmes of the partners in the consortium are presented in D6.1 and its update – D6.5.
REQ_COM_T6.2_3	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-9	D6.3 D6.4	REQUIRED	INSPECTION The education training kit is presented in this document.

ID	Priority	Traceability with objectives	WBS Deliverables	Compliance	Results
REQ_COM_T6.2_4	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-9	D6.3 D6.4	RECOMMENDED	INSPECTION The proposed recommendations will be tested during use cases demonstrations and reported in D7.7 document (M24)
REQ_COM_T6.2_5	P2	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7	D6.3 D6.4	OPTIONAL	INSPECTION/TEST The proposed triage training will be tested during use cases demonstrations within WP7.
REQ_BASE_T6.3_1	N/A	VALK-OBJ-7	D6.2 / D6.6 D6.3 D6.4	OPTIONAL	INSPECTION The information is presented in D6.2, D6.6, D6.3. Implementation is not covered by the project.
REQ_COM_T6.3_1	N/A	VALK-OBJ-7	D6.1 / D6.5	OPTIONAL	INSPECTION The information is presented in D6.1/D6.5. Implementation is not covered by the Project.
REQ_COM_T6.3_2	N/A	VALK-OBJ-7	D6.1 / D6.5	OPTIONAL	INSPECTION The information is presented in D6.1/D6.5. Implementation is not covered by the Project.
REQ_COM_T6.3_3	P2	VALK-OBJ-7	D6.1 / D6.5 D7.5-8	RECOMMENDED	INSPECTION The information is presented in D6.1/D6.5. Implementation is covered marginally, will be checked in WP7.

ID	Priority	Traceability with objectives	WBS Deliverables	Compliance	Results
REQ_COM_T6.3_4	P2	VALK-OBJ-7	D6.1 / D6.5 D7.5-8	OPTIONAL	INSPECTION The information is presented in D6.1/D6.5. Implementation is covered marginally, will be checked in WP7.
REQ_COM_T6.3_5	P2	VALK-OBJ-7	D6.2 / D6.6	RECOMMENDED	INSPECTION The information is presented in D6.2/D6.6.
REQ_COM_T6.3_6	N/A	VALK-OBJ-7	D6.1 / D6.5 D7.5-8	OPTIONAL	INSPECTION The information is presented in D6.1/D6.5. Implementation will be done in WP7.
REQ_BASE_T6.4_1	P1	All	D6.3 D6.4	REQUIRED	INSPECTION The information is presented in D6.5, D6.6, D6.3 and D6.4 submitted documents.
REQ_COM_T6.4_1	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-9	D6.1 / D6.5 D6.2 / D6.6 D6.3 D6.4	REQUIRED	INSPECTION The information is presented in D6.5, D6.6, D6.3 and D6.4 submitted documents.
REQ_COM_T6.4_2	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-9	D6.1 / D6.5 D6.2 / D6.6 D6.3 D6.4	REQUIRED	INSPECTION The areas of mutual interest between military and other participants in case of disasters are described in D6.5 and D6.6. Procedures, standards and some steps for harmonization of civil-military joint training are presented in D6.3 and D.6.4.

ID	Priority	Traceability with objectives	WBS Deliverables	Compliance	Results
REQ_COM_T6.4_3	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-9	D6.3 D6.4	RECOMMENDED	INSPECTION Training opportunity has been analysed and proposed in D6.6, D6.3 and D6.4 submitted documents.
REQ_BASE_T6.5_1	P1	VALK-OBJ-7	D6.3 D6.4	RECOMMENDED	INSPECTION Gaps and opportunities are presented in D6.6 submitted document.
REQ_COM_T6.5_1	P2	VALK-OBJ-1 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-9	D6.3 D6.4	RECOMMENDED	INSPECTION Study is presented in D6.5 submitted document.
REQ_COM_T6.5_2	P2	VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-9	D6.3 D6.4	RECOMMENDED	INSPECTION The information is presented in D6.5, D6.6, D6.3 and D6.4
REQ_COM_T6.5_3	P2	VALK-OBJ-6 VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-9	D6.3 D6.4	RECOMMENDED	INSPECTION Roadmap and gaps are presented in D6.3 and D6.4.
REQ_COM_T6.5_4	P2	VALK-OBJ-7 VALK-OBJ-9	D6.3 D6.4	RECOMMENDED	INSPECTION The information is presented in D6.3, D6.4.

Table 1 - WP6 Traceability Matrix

4. Methodology (common WP4, WP5 and WP6)

The methodology for the development of deliverable D6.4 was commonly agreed upon among the leaders of WP4, WP5 and WP6, and it is common for deliverables D4.4 and D5.4 and D6.4. NOVOTEC as framework harmonisation and INDRA as project leader supported this process.

The methodology followed in this deliverable has been to develop the opportunities that the project has arrived at through a logical reasoning process. It can be seen in detail in the deliverables on the harmonisation report. The core of the methodology is a SWOT analysis of each prioritised harmonisation opportunity followed by the VALKYRIES approach for its validation and roadmap for implementation.

In this last phase, the VALKYRIES project analyses the opportunities in depth and realises the first steps of these harmonisations building a proposal that will be tested in further stages of the project.

This deliverable is the end of the technical analysis of the harmonisation opportunities within the project, but it is the beginning of the specific development and can generate future projects.

5. Opportunities analysis

5.1. SWOT methodology (common)

SWOT analysis is a technique widely used in business to analyse a situation in order to make the right strategic decisions.

It is a systematic approach that facilitates analysis by distinguishing between the pros and cons of both the external and internal environment. In this way, 4 areas are defined which correspond to the acronym SWOT:

Strengths: They bring together the set of internal resources, positions of power and any type of competitive advantage specific to the agent under study.

Weaknesses: These are the aspects that limit the development capacity of the agent under study, due to its internal characteristics.

Opportunities: These are any factors external to the agent under study that favour its development or offer the possibility of implementing improvements.

Threats: These are all the external factors that could prevent the implementation of a strategy or jeopardise the viability of a proposal.

It can be represented graphically in 4 quadrants (figure 1):

Figure 1 – SWOT analysis matrix

This systematic SWOT approach has been applied by the project researchers to the assessment of the EU environment for each of the top 6 selected clustered opportunities.

Each analysis is preceded by a summary of the current EU landscape encountered in the previous phases of the project and includes a review of the main harmonisation efforts undertaken to date, all in relation to the specific scope of the clustered opportunities assessed.

6. Opportunity CO.WP6.11

This opportunity proposes definition of a minimum set of competencies and skills for volunteers for their successful integration in the operational procedures and to reach adequate volunteers' protection with risk-free activities.

The European Union (EU) has developed guidelines and recommendations to promote interoperability among emergency response organizations in different member states.

The EU's Directive 2007/33/EC on the implementation of the European Civil Protection Mechanism sets out a framework for cross-border cooperation in the event of disasters, including Mass Casualties Incidents (MCI). The directive requires member states to develop national civil protection systems and to establish a system for exchanging information and resources during emergencies.

The EU has also developed the European Civil Protection Pool (EUCP), which consists of resources, equipment, and experts from participating member states that can be deployed to provide assistance in the event of a disaster, including MCIs. The pool is intended to enhance the capacity of member states to respond to disasters and to facilitate cross-border cooperation. The EUCP includes a voluntary module that allows individuals with specific skills and expertise to register and be deployed to assist in emergency situations.

In addition, the EU has established the European Emergency Response Capacity (EERC), which provides training and exercises for emergency responders and promotes the development of common procedures and standards for emergency response.

6.1. SWOT evaluation

6.1.1. Strengths

- Increase integration and effectiveness of the involvement of volunteers in cross border MCI improving response times and reducing errors.
- Implementation of safety and risk-free activities of volunteers during assistance of the population in cross-border disaster reducing the risk of injury.
- Identified skills can be trained and standardised to increase volunteers' confidence and preparedness, which can improve their performance during MCI incidents.
- Better coordination and cooperation between military and civilian teams.
- The EU has developed legislation that allows for the implementation of measures that favour interoperability between agencies and the integration of volunteers into the different operational procedures.

6.1.2. Weaknesses

- Organisation and implementation of a practical and effective training useful for all the first aid responders, including volunteers involved in a cross-border MCI accepted and validated in all European countries.
- Motivation and participation of representatives of various institutions from the EU MS in selection and training for volunteers.
- Limited resources to provide volunteers with hands-on training or access to the latest technologies and equipment.

-
- Language barriers may prevent volunteers from fully understanding training materials and instructions.
 - The fact that the competences of volunteers are held by different institutions in the MS may be an obstacle in the standardisation process.

6.1.3. Opportunities

- Application of shared and universally accepted procedures and standards with the creation of national and European capabilities for effective response to natural disasters with mass casualties.
- Effective coordination and shared responsibilities between all actors involved in first aid responders, including volunteers.
- The use of new technologies can provide volunteers with realistic training scenarios and make easier the continuous training to update and improve their skills.
- Engaging with the local community to promote and offer training programs can help raise awareness and increase the number of volunteers.

6.1.4. Threats

- Limited participation of volunteers' organisations in common training.
- Some volunteers may not prioritize the training which can lead to a lack of interest and engagement.
- Some volunteers may be resistant to change and may be unwilling to participate in new or updated training programs.
- Volunteers may face legal liability for actions taken during MCI if the training is not adequate.

6.2. Scope of the VALKYRIES approach

The approach proposed by the VALKYRIES project includes the development of a curriculum, teaching methodology and qualification framework in order to conduct effective training for volunteers involved in multi-casualty incidents in collaboration with all the actors involved.

While there is no specific European training program for volunteers in cross-border MCI, VALKYRIES provides a framework for promoting interoperability and cooperation among emergency response organisations in different member states. At the moment, individual member states may have their own training programs and requirements for volunteers, but they are expected to be in line with the EU's guidelines and recommendations for civil protection and emergency response.

The details of the common curriculum and training course are best explained in Opportunity CO.WP6.05 and in Annex B.

The common curriculum and training courses for all actors involved in MCI is expected to reach an effective interaction and uniform procedures and standards in providing assistance in EU MS considering not only professional first responders but also volunteers.

6.3. Conclusions

This opportunity aims at having adequate standards, integration and safety procedures for volunteers involved in multi casualty incidents through creation of a common training program

with other actors involved in first aid response (civilian and military). This will ensure benefits of using the specific capabilities of all the actors involved in disasters, accidents and catastrophes. In addition, it will ensure safety of volunteers and risk-free activities.

7. Opportunity CO.WP6.2

The use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data in emergency situations can be a vital measure to ensure the security and privacy of information. However, as with any technological solution, there are internal and external factors that can affect its effectiveness and adoption.

7.1. SWOT evaluation

A SWOT (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats analysis) can help evaluate these factors and guide the implementation of appropriate cryptographic mechanisms in emergency situations.

7.1.1. Strengths

- Improves security and reduces the probability of data breach (unauthorised data access, manipulation, loss).
- HTTPS is a well know standard and widely used, which provides a good level of thrust and has a lot of technical support.
- Most of the mobile and low data rate networks support HTTPS overheads.
- Easy to update and upgrade the encryption keys/code and sw.
- Can be web / network distributed, does not requiring the more complex key distribution issues.

7.1.2. Weaknesses

- Legacy systems need to evolve to support https or use a proxy to share secure data.
- Adds delay and overhead, which affects the performance of slower networks.
- Adoption of cryptography may require technical expertise and resources that are not available in all organizations.
- Cryptographic mechanisms may be vulnerable to certain types of attacks, such as social engineering or exploitation of vulnerabilities in encryption systems.

7.1.3. Opportunities

- New technologies are under development based on quantum key distribution models, which can be further explored in the future.
- Develop a cross country automatic approval mechanisms for sharing data between the affected countries, for medical data.
- Cryptographic technologies are evolving.
- Awareness of the importance of data protection is growing, which may increase demand for cryptographic solutions.
- Governmental and non-governmental organizations can provide resources and support for the adoption of cryptographic mechanisms.

7.1.4. Threats

- The control over the security mechanisms in cross country may raise concerns over the entity that control the secure key and data distribution mechanisms.
- The trust approach model requires pre-validation of the entities entering in to the SIGRUN model, which puts more effort in the vetting process of the users granting access to the data.

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- Reliance on cryptographic mechanisms can lead to a false sense of security, which can lead to neglect of other important security measures.
 - Cryptographic solutions can be subject to sophisticated and persistent attacks by malicious actors, such as hackers, spies, or cybercriminals.

7.2. Scope of VALKYRIES approach

The process of harmonising the use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect the information in emergency situations involves several steps and stages that must be carefully followed to ensure the highest level of robustness in terms of information security and confidentiality. The key steps and stages of the process are presented below.

- Identification of information protection needs: The process of identifying information protection needs involves carefully assessing the type of information being handled, the degree of confidentiality required, and the number of people who will have access to the information, among other relevant factors. It is important to engage with key actors in the emergency situation, such as government authorities, rescue services, communications service providers and other relevant actors to identify the specific information protection needs in each case.

It is important to keep in mind that not all information handled in emergency situations requires the same protection, as personal and non-personal data could be involved, so a careful assessment needs to be made to determine what information requires additional protection measures and what type of protection is appropriate.

- Selecting the appropriate cryptographic mechanism: Once the information protection needs have been identified, the selection of the appropriate cryptographic mechanism for each case should proceed. It is important to carefully evaluate the different cryptographic mechanism options available and select the most appropriate one to protect the information in question.

Among the most common cryptographic mechanisms are symmetric key cryptography and public key cryptography. Symmetric key cryptography uses a single key shared between the sender and receiver to encrypt and decrypt information, while public key cryptography uses a different pair of keys, one public and one private, to encrypt and decrypt information.

It is important to evaluate strengths and weaknesses of each cryptographic mechanism and to select the most appropriate one for each specific case, considering factors such as the level of security required, complexity of implementation, cost and compatibility with other systems used in the emergency situation.

- Implementation of the selected cryptographic mechanism: The implementation of the selected cryptographic mechanism includes the installation and configuration of the necessary software and hardware on the communication and data storage systems used in the emergency situation. A planning and preparation process will be undertaken to ensure that the implementation is carried out effectively and efficiently. This will include allocating resources and trained personnel, preparing manuals and user guides for the personnel involved, conducting security tests, and defining monitoring and maintenance procedures.

To ensure that the cryptographic mechanism is effective and functions properly, it is important to conduct extensive testing prior to implementation in the production environment. This includes interoperability testing with other systems and equipment, performance testing and security testing. Once the cryptographic mechanism has been implemented, verification will be carried out to ensure that it is functioning properly.

- Compliance with the legal framework: Before implementing any cryptographic mechanism, it is important to consider the accomplishment of the legal provisions applicable to the given emergency situations. This stage may include reviewing local, national, and supranational laws and regulations governing personal and non-personal information protection, as well as the requirements applicable in the specific industry or sector in which the organisation is located.

In addition, it is important to consider the information security and privacy requirements established by applicable rules and regulations. For example, some laws may require that certain types of information shall be protected by specific cryptographic mechanisms and comply with certain security standards. This may require tailored advice in the assessment, including the involvement of legal experts, technology and information security lawyers, to ensure that all applicable legal and regulatory requirements are met.

- Training and awareness of the involved personnel: It is essential that staff involved in the management and protection of information in emergency situations are trained and aware of the importance of information security. A training and awareness programme will be conducted covering the following topics:
 - The basic concepts of cryptography and how the implemented cryptographic mechanism works.
 - Information security procedures and policies, including the importance of secure password management and the protection of confidential information.
 - The procedures for monitoring and maintaining the cryptographic mechanism.
 - Secure communication and data storage practices in emergency situations.

Training and awareness of the personnel involved should be continuous and regularly updated to ensure that they are aware of the latest information security practices and procedures.

7.3. Conclusions

The process of harmonising the use of cryptographic mechanisms to protect data in emergency situations can benefit from a SWOT analysis. The identification of strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats can be useful in developing strategies that maximise the benefits and minimise the risks associated with the use of cryptography in emergency situations.

In addition, SWOT analysis can help align the interests and objectives of the different actors involved in the harmonisation process, including governmental organisations, non-governmental organisations, and private companies. This can be especially important to address

identified threats and weaknesses, such as possible government regulation or lack of technical resources in some organisations.

In conclusion, SWOT analysis can be a useful tool to assess and guide the process of harmonising the use of cryptographic mechanisms in emergency situations. By identifying and addressing the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats associated with the use of cryptography, the protection of data in critical situations can be maximised and an effective and sustainable implementation of these tools can be ensured.

Guidelines for harmonising the use of cryptographic mechanisms in emergency situations include identifying protection needs, selecting an appropriate mechanism, training staff, and considering legal and regulatory aspects.

Lessons learned include the importance of a careful and strategic approach and the critical protection of information in emergency situations.

8. Opportunity CO.WP6.7

This opportunity proposes the use of Virtual Operation Support Teams (VOSTs) in cross-border MCI.

8.1. SWOT evaluation

SWOT analysis of this opportunity defines strengths and weaknesses which are internal factors and opportunities and threats which are external factors determining the harmonisation of this opportunity.

8.1.1. Strengths

- Integration of volunteers – use of VOSTs does not require permanent staff, in most countries where VOSTs work on daily basis, the core staff is made of volunteers.
- Skill set and motivation – members of VOSTs have skills in computer science, journalism, law enforcement, public health and many others (for example they are former firefighters, or policemen or worked for other emergency-related organisation).
- Networks of networks – national and international VOSTs work together – for example VOST Spain operates at national level but is strongly connected with VOSTs in autonomous communities.
- Agility and flexibility – VOSTs can quickly mobilize and adapt to changing circumstances.
- Remote capabilities – VOSTs operate remotely, allowing them to provide support from anywhere with an internet connection.
- Real-Time information – VOSTs can monitor social media and other digital channels in real-time, allowing them to quickly identify and respond to emerging issues.
- Data analysis – VOSTs can provide valuable data analysis and mapping services. This can be used to inform decision-making and resource allocation.

8.1.2. Weaknesses

- Coordination and integration – since VOSTs are mainly organised as digital volunteers, its coordination with, and integration in the formal emergency management method depends on the authorities who are in charge at regional/local and national level.
- Training and motivation – VOSTs do not receive any training from emergency managers; without formal training or exercise without a background in emergency management or similar, they can hardly become as suitable partners.
- Dependence on technology – Digital teams rely on digital tools and platforms. In the event of an internet of power outage, VOSTs may be unable to provide support.
- Volunteer Management – while VOSTs are designed to facilitate communication and collaboration, there can still be communication challenges, especially in situations where there are language barriers, cultural differences, or technical difficulties.

8.1.3. Opportunities

- Support situational awareness.
- Technology advancements – the rapid pace of technology advancements provides an opportunity for VOSTs to improve their operations and capabilities.
- Counter rumours and disseminate official communication.

- Emergency and disaster management practices can transform from static to dynamic – network-based arrangements.
- Use (or in some countries creation) of VOSTs can become a fast-evolving environment with involvement of new technologies.
- Global reach - VOSTs have the potential to operate on a global scale, providing support and assistance to emergency response and disaster relief efforts around the world.

8.1.4. Threats

- Low support from local/regional and national authorities and people in charge according to emergency management cycle.
- Budgetary issues - digital volunteers rely on donations mainly, which can be unpredictable and inconsistent.
- Cybersecurity risks – VOSTs use technology and digital platforms which can make them vulnerable to cyber-attacks and hacking.
- Misinformation and disinformation.

8.2. Scope of VALKYRIES approach

It is important to state, that creation/improvements of VOSTs itself are out of the scope of this project. Focus is given on incorporation of information, which VOST is producing into the information flow of the first responders. How this information could be presented to the C2 post and to the Incident commander, respectively to other related actors.

For the testing in the UCs, it is expected that the “VOST information” (several notices) will be prepared in advance (so it will not be real VOST outputs), and will be putted into the communication system. Information will be for example *“in close by and densely populated area, about 10 kilometres from the incident, south and by wind direction, many social media posts were captured. People can see a cloud from the fire. Many pictures are shared between them. They are not mentioning any breathing problems or health issues”* or *“from the next village (should be named) in south and by wind direction, distance about 15 kilometres form the incident, no posts related to the incident (fire, cloud, plume) have been detected”*, respectively there might be also information that in certain area people are complaining about breathing issues, blisters formation and another related symptoms which indicate, that the toxicity of the cloud in that particular distance is still dangerous.

The way of technical implementation relies on project technical partners. Test will be focused on assessment if it is displayed/presented to the first responders in an optimal way, if this information is helpful and how such an information can affect decision making of responders and so the response action at all. Training is not needed, just an information about VOST and the fact, that such an information might be available in communication system. Validation will be performed via debriefing (questionnaires/surveys) with the exercise participants.

8.3. Conclusions

Actions of VOSTs is still something new and not fully explored. It represents great potential to improve response action, as it can provide valuable information to the responders. This represents VOSTs novelty at the same time. Once such an information is gathered and verified,

it needs to be forwarded to the communication system of responders to enable them to use this information in optimal way.

Communication management in crisis situations is key in an interconnected society. Currently, the main route of communication of emergencies are social networks, representing both an opportunity thanks to the rapid dissemination of information and a challenge due to the great presence of hoaxes and false news.

Among the private initiatives to support administrations in the management of crises in a digital scenario, the Virtual Operation Support Team (VOST) appears.

American Red Cross launched the first Digital Operations Centre in 2011 in Washington, extending both throughout the Americas, Europe and Oceania. Currently these teams exist in New Zealand, Italy, Portugal, Spain, Slovakia, among others.

The focus of activities within the VALKYRIES project is given directly to this data transfer and their presentation in the respondents' information system.

9. Opportunity CO.WP6.5

This opportunity proposes the standardization of education and training for first aid responses (creation of a training kit: curriculum, training methodology and training manual).

In Europe, the standardization of education and training for first aid responses is governed by the European Resuscitation Council (ERC). The ERC is a non-profit organization that aims to improve the quality of resuscitation in Europe through the development and promotion of resuscitation guidelines, education, and training.

The ERC provides a standardised curriculum for first aid training that is based on the latest scientific evidence and best practices in the field of resuscitation. The training is designed to be accessible to all individuals, regardless of their level of medical knowledge or experience.

The ERC also provides guidelines for the certification and accreditation of first aid training providers, to ensure that the training they provide meets the highest standards of quality and safety. These guidelines cover the content and duration of the training courses, as well as the qualifications and experience required of the trainers.

In the context of a MCI, the European standardization of education and training for first aid responses is guided by the European Trauma Course (ETC). The ETC is a comprehensive training program that focuses on the initial management of patients with traumatic injuries in the pre-hospital setting.

The ETC provides a standardized curriculum for first aid training in the context of an MCI and guidelines for the certification and accreditation of first aid training providers in the context of an MCI, to ensure that the training they provide meets the highest standards of quality and safety.

In addition, EUCPM has established a framework for cooperation and coordination in the event of a cross-border MCI, including the standardization of education and training for first aid responses. This framework includes:

1. Standardized training and certification: The EUCPM promotes the development of standardized training programs and certification requirements for first aid responders involved in cross-border MCIs.
2. Mutual recognition of qualifications: The EUCPM encourages EU member states and participating countries to recognize the qualifications and certifications of first aid responders from other countries, to facilitate their deployment in cross-border MCIs.
3. Information sharing: The EUCPM facilitates the sharing of information and best practices among participating countries, to improve the effectiveness and coordination of the response to cross-border MCIs.
4. Joint exercises and training events: The EUCPM organises joint exercises and training events for first aid responders from different countries, to enhance their skills and promote collaboration in emergency situations.

9.1. SWOT evaluation

The SWOT analysis is focused on the identification of what will be the expected positive results from the implementation of this opportunity, as well as some expected difficulties and threats

that must be considered in the process of harmonisation of first aid preparedness and cross-sectorial collaboration in case of cross-border MCI.

9.1.1. Strengths

- The implementation of suggested opportunity will respond to the need of development, validation, certification and pre-standardisation of a Joint multinational and multidisciplinary training of first responders. Cross-border cooperation in MCI requires comparable knowledge bases and to be able to provide equivalent services between the EU Member States (MS).
- Besides, the implementation of this opportunity will improve interoperability and will enhance collaboration among first responders in cross-border MCI.
- Moreover, an advanced education and training kit for first responders focused on cross-border MCI at the European level and according to national guidelines would align the different EU MS and their first responders would be able to work in a more effective way in different MS.
- The EU is committed to the promotion of civil protection, including the training of emergency services professionals.

9.1.2. Weaknesses

- There exist hundreds of courses for first responders, and even though in most cases, training for is done separately for medical teams and other first responders (civil protection, firefighters, police, military, volunteers, etc.), as well as the national level focus, there might be a serious competition. We need to prove the novelty, uniqueness and the appropriateness of the suggested training.
- It might take long time to validate, certify, get accreditation and standardise at the EU level the suggested training course.
- There are many regulatory and procedural differences and practices among the EU MS regarding training of first responders, which might be a serious issue to overcome.
- Finally, the implementation of the suggested opportunity is related to mind-set change and the established way of work of first responders because they will be trained to work in multinational and interagency environment in a case of cross-border MCI. The data from some of the interviews that were carried out in the framework of WP4, WP5 and W6 shows that there are first responders that think the collaboration opportunities in the framework EUCPM is enough and there is no need of any additional effort to be done.

9.1.3. Opportunities

- To train first responders in new technological solutions to enhance their abilities and capabilities to fight off the consequences of disasters. The analysis of the education and training gaps revealed that some of the first responders are not ready to use these technologies. There is a need for to sufficiently improve their training to operate cutting edge software, hardware or equipment.
- Creation of a common base for FR training by defining the desired competencies for training for cross-border MCI and disasters.

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- The implementation of this opportunity will fill several described in D6.6 capability gaps: (1) Lack of standard for cross-border recognition of first aid courses; (2) Lack of first responders' training in new technological solutions; (3) Need to define the minimum set of required competencies for training of first responders for MCI and disasters; (4) Need of joint multinational training for first responders.
 - The aforementioned process of standardisation of training for first aid response would serve as a roadmap for rescuers to devise and implement a system of continuous improvement and self-assessment, which can be followed by a process of accreditation and external recognition through progressive certification of resources, services and protocols for emergency rescue response.

9.1.4. Threats

- Lack of funding to continue working on the process of validation, certification, accreditation at the EU level the training course after initial demonstration in the UCs and after the project ends.
- Lack of interest of the VALKYRIES partners to proceed with the next steps for standardisation of the suggested harmonisation opportunity.
- Difficulties to identify EU institution that can take the lead and the responsibility for certification, accreditation and standardisation at the EU level of the course.

9.2. Scope of VALKYRIES approach

The analyses of the landscape of education and training for first aid responses in Europe carried out in D6.1 and the update D6.5 revealed that in most cases, training is done separately for medical teams and other first responders (civil protection, firefighters, police, military, volunteers, etc.). Besides, most of the courses are thought at the national level. Moreover, there is a lack of training on how first responders use advanced technological solutions to improve the effectiveness of their work together. There is a clear need to train first responders together both at national and international levels. The Education and Training (E&T) of first aid responders vary within European countries. Cross-border cooperation in MCI requires comparable knowledge bases and being able to provide equivalent services between the EU Member States (MS).

The suggested education and training harmonisation opportunity for first aid responses will help to bridge for capability gaps, identified in D6.6:

- G6.2-2: Lack of standard for cross-border recognition of first aid courses;
- G6.2-11: Lack of first responders' training in new technological solutions;
- G6.2-12: Knowledge, skills and competency spread between various groups of healthcare professionals who are tasked to participate in the management of MCI;
- G6.2-22: Insufficient joint multinational training for first responders.

The implementation of this opportunity is related to the creation of a Joint multinational and multidisciplinary training kit for different groups of First Responders who need to acquire basic knowledge and practical skills for performing life-saving activities in various types of trauma and

medical conditions in case of cross-border MCI. This training kit contains curriculum, training methodology and training content/presentations.

The curriculum includes specific skills and knowledge that are (1) necessary for the individual to provide first aid with a limited amount of equipment; (2) to recognize the emergency, activate an EMS system and serve as liaisons with other emergency services, fire brigade, military, police (Annex B).

The whole duration of the course is 8 hrs per day for 3 days. It is organised in several modules. The first seven modules cover topics related to the basic knowledge and practical skills for first responders to perform life-saving activities such as:

- Introduction to the first responders' role;
- Airway, breathing and circulation;
- Cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR) for basic life support;
- Wound management. Stop the bleeding;
- Fractures. Stabilizing injured extremity;
- Management of thermal/cold injury;
- Medical emergencies.

In addition to the basic medical training, there is a special module entitled "Disaster preparedness and transportation" which focuses on national, international and cross-border legal frameworks and procedures for interaction in the field of prevention, preparedness and response to large-scale emergencies, natural and man-made disasters and fires, as well as the terms and conditions for helping in the event of a disaster. Besides, this module aims at providing knowledge regarding tools for data management and exchange, safety procedures, the infrastructure and access to medical resources, CBRN issues, etc.

Finally, the focus of the course is on planning and organisation of training of first responders on how to use the VALKYRIES solution/tools (communication, data management and protection, digitalised triage, use of wearables) and demonstration during the UCs. The specific training to use the tools will be according to the needs and roles of the first responders, as well as the situation and planning of the exercises. The methodology includes online induction training and up to 8 hrs of onsite training before/during the exercises).

The trainings will be focused on the following tools:

- ARATOS.Net Earth Observation Data Platform;
- INDRA: iSAFETY Application Modules for C2;
- PARTICLE's Platform for Enhanced Situational Awareness and Secure Communications (GLOBAL COP);
- TASSICA 3 Triage card – TASSICA APP (TASSICA);
- ARATOS and BlockChain2050 bracelet Tap2SOS;
- MONITOR HOSPITALS.

9.3. Conclusions

The implementation of this harmonisation opportunity is expected to enhance the work of first responders in case of cross-border MCI by providing knowledge and skills in several key areas. First, awareness of emergency conditions and/or the proper extent of injuries which require first aid. Second, ability to administer appropriate first aid for life threatening injuries (relative to airway, breathing and circulation). Third, evacuation/transport of the victim to medical care facility. Fourth, assist health care providers. Fourth, use of modern digital tools for triage, enhanced situational awareness, data management and protection, communication and information exchange, etc.

The most important strength of the training kit is the focus on new technological VALKYRIES solutions, which can greatly facilitate first responders in their operations. The fact is that if first responders are not sufficiently trained to use these technological solutions beforehand, this may result in reluctance and attachment in older and less effective actions.

Lessons learned: Investment in technological innovation in care and training of health professionals is a slow and heterogeneous process that depends on factors external to the institutions involved in VALKYRIES project. The resilience of professionals to new technologies is another important aspect to be addressed by responsible institutions.

Guidelines for implementation of the opportunity: There are at least two EU institutions that might be interested to support the process of harmonisation and pre-standardisation of this opportunity at the EU level. These are the European Agency for Safety and Health at Work and the European Committee for First Aid Education (EC First Aid).

10. Opportunity CO.WP6.10

This opportunity proposes the use of common procedures and standards for training and civil-military actions.

The EU has established a common approach to Civil-Military Cooperation (CIMIC), which includes the standardization of education and training for CIMIC personnel.

The NATO CIMIC Centre of Excellence (CCOE) as a part of European Security and Defence College is responsible for the development and implementation of the European Standard for CIMIC training. The European Standard for CIMIC training provides a common set of guidelines and standards for the training of CIMIC personnel across the EU to collaborate effectively with civilian organizations in support of crisis management operations.

The European Standard for CIMIC training covers the following key areas:

- CIMIC fundamentals: This includes an understanding of the principles, objectives, and functions of CIMIC, as well as the legal and policy frameworks governing CIMIC.
- Communication and negotiation skills: This covers the development of effective communication and negotiation skills to facilitate collaboration and cooperation between military forces and civilian organizations.
- Crisis management and planning: This covers the development of crisis management and planning skills, including risk assessment, decision-making, and the coordination of resources.
- Cultural awareness and sensitivity which includes the development of cultural awareness and sensitivity skills, to facilitate effective communication and collaboration across different cultures and backgrounds.
- Training and exercise design: This covers the development of training and exercise design skills, to ensure that CIMIC personnel are properly trained and prepared to respond to crisis situations.

10.1. SWOT evaluation

The SWOT analysis includes an assessment of the strengths and weaknesses, opportunities and threats that can accompany the realization of this opportunity not only within the scope of the project, but also within the EU countries.

10.1.1. Strengths

- Raising awareness of the benefits of military involvement assisting civil institutions in catastrophic disasters.
- Implementation of developed and mastered joint practical procedures for assisting the population in cross-border disasters.
- Building capabilities to implement joint civil-military procedures in disasters, accidents and catastrophes.
- Better coordination and cooperation between military and civilian teams.

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- There are countries where civil-military integration in civil emergencies is already implemented with very good results.

10.1.2. Weaknesses

- Timely course certification can be a problem due to complex procedures and coordination between institutions.
- Some EU countries could object to such training due to limited use of the armed forces in disaster protection and public assistance in emergency situations.
- Organizing and conducting the course within the framework of the European Security and Defence College may encounter bureaucratic obstacles and to be delayed.
- The motivation and participation of representatives of various institutions from the EU countries can be weak and unsatisfactory.

10.1.3. Opportunities

- Application of common procedures and standards in case of emergencies.
- Building national and EU capabilities for effective response to natural disasters with mass casualties.
- Effective coordination and shared responsibilities between military teams and civilian first aid responses.
- The fact that professionals from different backgrounds, with different training and experience, converge in emergency response makes cooperation enriching and provides professionals with a broad view of disaster management.

10.1.4. Threats

- Insufficient understanding of the purpose, tasks and effectiveness of CIMIC coordination and interaction.
- Limited participation of representatives of civil institutions and EU countries.

10.2. Scope of VALKYRIES approach

The approach proposed by VALKYRIES includes the development of a methodology, qualification framework and curriculum for conducting joint interagency training of military and civilian response teams in case of cross-border MCI.

The scope of the course does not include military training for the civilian population as a whole, but only for experts and specialists who will be involved in liquidating the consequences of catastrophic large-scale disasters and emergencies. These are military and civilian specialists from the medical services, fire protection services and departments, police and local government, as well as volunteers. The main goal of the course is to create a centralised improvement of the understanding and use of common procedures and training programs for response in Joint Emergency Actions, based on experiences and lessons learned, and covers the emergency spectrum. The focus of the training of specialists from various fields for the understanding of possibilities for interaction in emergency situations, resulting from natural disasters with mass casualties and destructions.

The methodology includes developing the knowledge and skills of the trainees in matters related to the foundations of CIMIC and the practical-applied aspects of the planning and management of activities in Emergency Situations, crises and disasters of any nature. Also, the trainees must become familiar with the main approaches and ways of building capabilities for civil-military interaction in emergencies. In addition, the trainees acquire mandatory knowledge, respectively sufficient abilities and skills at a practical-applied level, regarding the main guidelines, mechanisms and approaches for organizing civil-military interaction activities and synchronizing efforts between all structures, forces and resources in conditions of various emergency situations.

The main issues that will be studied are the essence, principles, functions, goals and tasks of civil-military cooperation, legal and other aspects of joint civil-military activity, the organization of joint multinational and interagency actions, procedures for civil-military interaction and for emergency civil-military cooperation planning, procedures and standards for training and civil-military operations in the emergency area.

After completing the course, trainees should know the essence, goals, tasks and opportunities for interaction; the functional and legal aspects for carrying out the joint activities; the essence of the guiding documents for organising CIMIC activities in joint multinational actions. They must be able to apply the basic principles and policies of CIMIC and civil defence; quickly make decisions in accordance with joint standards and procedures in conditions of time and resource deficit; to act flexibly and adaptively, taking calculated and justified risk; work successfully in multinational teams; effectively communicate ideas, views (written and verbal) and motivate teams to support the chosen course of action when conducting joint civil-military activities.

The duration is 3 days (810 minutes), includes 11-hours lectures, 7-hours exercises, self-study and training ends with an exam. The training curriculum comprise lectures, discussions, research and study of the following documents and training materials: Allied Joint Doctrine for the Military Contribution to Humanitarian Assistance; Handbook of CIMIC specialists; Joint CIMIC Manual; Joint Tactics, Technics and Procedures (TTPs). Moreover, by the end of the project, we intend to develop and offer a Handbook/Manual with steps, procedures and guidelines for joint Civil-Military Interaction (CMI) in case of emergencies. This will support the building of capabilities for effective interaction and the use of uniform procedures and standards when providing assistance in cross-border incidents on the territory of EU countries.

10.3. Conclusions

This capability provides for the application of joint civil-military procedures and standards in the training of military and civilian teams. This will ensure a common understanding of the benefits of using the specific capabilities of the military to support civilian institutions in disasters, accidents and catastrophes. In addition, it will ensure the achievement of better coordination and cooperation between military and civilian teams at MCIs.

Finally, it will spearhead the development of joint national and common European capabilities for the joint participation of military and civilian teams and will improve a common Civil-Military Interaction in response to cross-border natural emergencies with multi casualties.

11. WP6 Conclusions

This final part of the deliverable summarizes the conclusions from the analysis of the harmonisation opportunities at the WP6 level.

The result from the analysis of the top-5 ranked collaboration, education and training opportunities shows that there are very important strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats that must be considered in the process of harmonisation and pre-standardisation at the EU level.

Among the most important strengths are: First, enhanced interoperability and better coordination among first responders from different national and international institutions; Second, increased safety of the people on the terrain; Third, improved security and reduced probability of data breach in trans-border MCI; Fourth, better agility and flexibility of the teams involved in the MCI; Fifth, building capabilities to implement joint civil-military procedures in disasters, accidents and catastrophes, and as a whole better preparedness for implementation of the duties of the first responder.

Among the most important weaknesses are: first, the existing language barriers that may prevent first responders from fully understanding training materials and instructions; Second, the adoption of cryptography may require technical expertise and resources that are not available in all organizations; third, the cryptographic mechanisms may be vulnerable to certain types of attacks, such as social engineering or exploitation of vulnerabilities in encryption systems; fourth, VOSTs do not receive any formal training from emergency managers and they are highly dependent on digital technology; fifth, It might take long time to validate, certify, get accreditation and standardise at the EU level the suggested training courses; sixth, there are many regulatory and procedural differences and practices among the EU MS regarding training of first responders, which might be a serious issue to overcome; seventh, some EU countries could object to such training due to limited use of the armed forces in disaster protection and public assistance in emergency situations.

Along with the strengths and weaknesses described, there are important opportunities that need also to be considered not to miss any of them. Among the most important opportunities are first, effective coordination and shared responsibilities between all actors involved in first aid responders including volunteers; second, develop a cross country automatic approval mechanisms for sharing data between the affected countries, for medical data; third, emergency and disaster management practices can transform from static to dynamic – network-based arrangements; fourth, train first responders in new technological solutions to enhance their abilities and capabilities to fight off the consequences of disasters; fifth, creation of a common base for FR training by defining the desired competencies for training for cross-border MCI and disasters; sixth, effective coordination and shared responsibilities between military teams and civilian first aid responses.

Finally, the analysis revealed several possible threats to harmonization and pre-standardisation of collaboration, education and training for first aid responses that are related to: first, some volunteers may not prioritize the training which can lead to a lack of interest and engagement; second, volunteers may face legal liability for actions taken during MCI incidents if the training

is not adequate; third, reliance on cryptographic mechanisms can lead to a false sense of security, which can lead to neglect of other important security measures; fourth, cryptographic solutions can be subject to sophisticated and persistent attacks by malicious actors, such as hackers, spies, or cybercriminals; fifth, cybersecurity risks – VOSTs use technology and digital platforms which can make them vulnerable to cyber-attacks and hacking; sixth, lack of funding to continue working on the process of validation, certification, accreditation at the EU level the training course after initial demonstration and testing in the UCs and after the project ends; seventh, lack of interest of the VALKYRIES partners to proceed with the next steps for standardisation of the suggested training courses; eighth, challenging to identify EU institution that can take the lead and the responsibility for certification, accreditation and standardisation at the EU level of the course, ninth, insufficient understanding of the purpose, tasks and effectiveness of CIMIC coordination and interaction in cross-border MCI.

12. Annex A – Glossary

Acronym	Description
CCOE	CIMIC Centre of Excellence
CIMIC	Civil-Military Cooperation
CMI	Civil-Military Interaction
EERC	European Emergency Response Capacity
EMS	Emergency Medical Service
ERC	European Resuscitation Council
ETC	European Trauma Course
EU	European Union
EUCPM	European Union Civil Protection Mechanism
EUCP	European Civil Protection Pool
MCI	Multi-casualty Incident
MS	EU Member States
VOSTs	Virtual Operation Support Teams

Table 2 - Glossary

13. Annex B – JOINT MULTINATIONAL FIRST RESPONDERS TRAINING CURRICULUM

Introduction

First Responder is the first person on the scene to recognize the emergency, activate an Emergency Medical Service (EMS) system and provide lifesaving first aid with minimal equipment until the EMS providers arrive.

This curriculum includes specific skills and knowledge to be acquired by first responders in case of cross-border Multi Casualty Incidents (MCI):

- Skills, necessary for the individual to provide first aid with a limited amount of equipment;
- Knowledge to recognize the emergency, activate an EMS system and serve as liaisons with other emergency services, fire brigade, military, police, etc.
- Lessons learned after successful completion of the program:
- Recognize emergency conditions or the proper extent of injuries which require first aid;
- Administer appropriate first aid for life threatening injuries (relative to airway, breathing and circulation);
- Evacuation/transport of the victim to medical care facility;
- Assist health care providers.

Minimum entry requirements: everyone (18 years and older). Healthcare providers and emergency responders aren't the only ones required to have passed first aid training. Nursing home employees, civilians, volunteers, lifeguards, flight attendants, some construction jobs and even teachers are also required to have current training in basic lifesaving skills. All workplaces should have trained first responders when there are more than 10-25 employees.

Minimum Course duration

To be qualified in the field of First Responder, it is recommended that training programme would be of 24 hours' duration (3 days, 8 hours daily) and would be a mix of didactic, video-based, interactive lectures and hands-on practice. Some training modules may be customized according to the target population and the specifics of first responder's role (medics, paramedics, firefighters, police, volunteers, etc.)

Course Participants: A maximum of 60-75 candidates per course.

Teaching faculty and infrastructure:

Course director: 1 – medical doctor with at least 5 years of experience in emergency medicine with adequate training;

Core Faculty: 4-5 – medical doctors and paramedics (who has passed basic first responder course successfully), nurses, firefighters, technology providers.

Language: To guarantee interoperability among first responders, English is the official languages for all the subjects of study and for examination of the course.

PART 1: INTRODUCTION TO THE FIRST RESPONDER' ROLE – 3 HOURS.

Learning Outcomes: At the completion of this part, the student should be able to:

- Understand the first responder's duties and responsibilities;
- Apprehend the extent of his/her abilities and look for supervision when emergency situations are away from one's competence and authority;
- Understand relevant medico-legal principles of providing first aid response in cross-border Multi casualty incidents (MCI);
- Be aware of the importance of interpersonal communication skills and the teamwork;
- Learn how to rapidly identify changing emergency situations and quickly adapt, by managing data;
- Obey the principles for first aid and triage;
- Be aware of his/her role in the preparedness for cross-border disaster management;
- Personal protection and safety procedures.

PART 2: AIRWAY, BREATHING AND CIRCULATION.

Learning Outcomes: At the completion of this module, the student should be able to:

- Assess airways and breathing for emergencies;
- Provide measures to ensure clear airways;
- Apply manoeuvres concerning free airways if needed;
- Manage with airway obstruction caused by foreign body;
- Preventing aspiration;
- Assess breathing (if a patient is with pathological type of breathing);
- Evaluate the cardiac status of the patient;
- Stop haemorrhage - pressure/tourniquets.

DAY 1

No.	Topics	Duration
1.	Introduction to the healthcare delivery system, emergency conditions, triage and the golden hour.	15 min.
2.	Duties and responsibilities of a first responder.	15 min

No.	Topics	Duration
3.	Professionalism, ethical and legal issues and well-being of the First responder.	15 min
4.	Anatomy of the Human Body.	35 min
5.	Airway obstruction. Manoeuvres and management of preventing aspiration and foreign body obstruction.	35 min
6.	Breathing. Steps in providing ventilation.	35 min
7.	Circulation and cardiac status.	35 min
8.	Haemorrhage and control of bleeding. Pressure bandage and tourniquet.	35 min
9.	External and internal bleeding. Wound care.	35 min
10.	Cardiac arrest and cardiopulmonary resuscitation.	35 min
11.	Fractures. Rules and materials used for splinting.	35 min
12.	First aid for thermal/cold injuries.	35 min
Total hours per day		6 hours 30 min
Breaks / lunch time /coffee breaks		1 hour 30 min

PART 3: CARDIOPULMONARY RESUSCITATION (CPR) for basic life support.

Learning Outcomes: At the completion of this part, the student should be able to:

- Determine the need for CPR, steps for performing it and when to stop or not to beginning;
- Perform Cardiopulmonary resuscitation.

PART 4: WOUND MANAGEMENT. STOP THE BLEEDING.

Learning Outcomes: At the completion of this module, the student should be able to:

- Make a difference between arterial and venous bleeding;
- Evaluate the patients' condition and take appropriate action in case of bleeding;
- Stop external bleeding;
- Identify internal bleeding;
- Apply tourniquet, dressings and bandages.

PART 5: FRACTURES. STABILISING INJURED EXTREMITY.

Learning Outcomes: At the completion of this module, the student should be able to:

-
- Identify injuries to muscles and bones;
 - Follow the rules for splinting;
 - Be familiar with materials used;
 - Understand the importance of splinting in case of bone/spinal injury.

PART 6: MANAGEMENT OF THERMAL/COLD INJURY.

Learning Outcomes: At the completion of this module, the student should be able to:

- Evaluate the patients' condition and take appropriate action in case of burn/cold injury;
- Size up the site of burn/cold injury and take appropriate action;
- Apply appropriate resuscitation and dressings to help a victim of burn/cold injury.

PART 7: MEDICAL EMERGENCIES.

Learning Outcomes: At the completion of this module, the student should be able to:

- Identify patient with common medical emergencies (angina/myocardial infarction, stroke, heat stroke, allergy, fainting/seizures, low/high blood sugar, poisoning);
- Follow the steps in providing first aid to a patient with general medical complaints.

PART 8: DISASTER PREPAREDNESS AND TRANSPORTATION.

Learning Outcomes: At the completion of this module, the student should be able to:

- Determine the hazards in different disaster settings (natural disasters - earthquakes or flooding, man-made disasters – CBRN, explosions or chemical spills or a combination of both);
- Avoid significant safety risks posed by instability of the environment (aftershocks following an earthquake);
- Take timely, managed, controlled, coordinated and effective response measures in the event of occurrence of CBRN disaster to mitigate the consequences (minimize risks to health, life and environment);
- Be familiar with the infrastructure and the access to medical resources;
- Be familiar with legal national, international and cross-border frameworks and projects for interaction in the field of prevention, preparedness and response to large-scale emergencies, natural and man-made disasters and fires, as well as the terms and conditions for providing assistance in the event of a disaster;
- Be familiar with Tools for information management and exchange;
- Make decisions what help might be available and how to access it;
- Understand the importance of timely and proper transportation.

DAY 2

No.	Topics	Duration (Theory/Practical)
1.	Medical emergencies - myocardial infarction, stroke.	35 min theory.
2.	Medical emergencies – allergy, poisoning.	35 min theory
3.	Medical emergencies - fainting/seizures, low/high blood sugar levels.	35 min theory
4.	Natural disasters – risks, emergency plan, emergency kit.	35 min theory
5.	CBRN disasters – risks, first aid, evacuation plan.	35 min theory
6.	National, international and cross-border frameworks and projects for interaction in case of disaster events	35 min theory
7.	Cardiac arrest and cardiopulmonary resuscitation.	30 min practical
8.	Removing a foreign body airway obstruction.	30 min practical
9.	CPR- videos and mannequins for performing it.	25 min practical
10.	Wound care –dressings and bandages.	25 min practical
11.	Arterial bleeding – tourniquet.	25 min practical
12.	Bone fractures and spine injury – first aid.	30 min practical
13.	Thoracic and abdominal injuries – first aid.	25 min practical
14.	Heat/cold trauma – first aid.	25 min practical
15.	CBRN events – first aid.	25 min. practical
Total hours per day		6 hours 30 min
Breaks / lunch time /coffee time		1 hour 30 min

DAY 3

SPECIALISED TRAINING OF FIRST RESPONDERS TO USE THE VALKYRIES SOLUTIONS FOR PROVIDING FIRST AID RESPONSE IN CROSS-BORDER MULTI CASUALTY INCIDENTS

No.	Tools for enhancing crisis management information exchange; Platforms for improved Situational Awareness; Digitalisation of triage. Learn and apply in cross-border MCI scenarios.	Duration (on-line and onsite training)
1.	ARATOS.Net Earth Observation Data Platform.	35 min. on-line training
2.	INDRA: iSAFETY Application Modules for C2.	35 min. on-line training
3.	PARTICLE's Platform for Enhanced Situational Awareness and Secure Communications (GLOBAL COP).	35 min. on-line training
4.	TASSICA 3 Triage card – TASSICA APP (TASSICA).	35 min. on-line training
5.	ARATOS and BlockChain2050 bracelet Tap2SOS;	35 min. on-line training
6.	MONITOR HOSPITALS (HESE).	30 min. on-line training
7.	Applying data in Net Earth Observation Data Platform in multi-casual scenario.	35 min. onsite training
8.	Applying data in iSAFETY Application Modules for C2.	35 min. onsite training
9.	Patient data, triage and exchange of information using GLOBAL COP.	30 min. onsite training
10.	Scenario with multi-casual incident – insert data in the Triage card.	30 min. onsite training
11.	BlockChain2050 Bracelet – the advantage of knowing patient's medical history. Scenario with unconscious patient.	30 min. onsite training
Total hours per day		7 hours 30 min
Breaks/coffee time		30 min

REFERENCES:

1. European Prevention Curriculum (EUPC), Pub. Author: EMCDDA, ISBN: 978-92-9497-416-7, ISSN: 1606-1705. DOI: 10.2810/852697, Catalog Number: TDMA19001ENC
2. Medexpress Companies, Emergency Medical Responder, Course Syllabus. Available at: <http://www.medexpresscompanies.com/uploads/EMRCourseSyllabusSchedule.pdf>.
3. United States Department of Transportation National Highway Traffic Safety Administration First Responder: National Standard Curriculum. Available on - https://www.ems.gov/pdf/education/First-Responder/FR_1995.pdf.

14. Annex C – Basic training curriculum for Joint CIMIC Training Program

Introduction

Civil-military cooperation can be particularly valuable in the context of a large-scale cross-border disaster with multiple casualties and destruction. Military teams can provide important and unique assistance through their medical teams, transport vehicles for evacuation and transport of assets, for monitoring and evaluating results in the affected area, for maintaining security and public order, and more. For this purpose, it is important to build joint capabilities for civil-military interaction and coordination of efforts, which requires knowledge of the principles, rules, standards and procedures for such cooperation.

This curriculum includes specific skills and knowledge to be acquired by civilian and military first responders to cross-border Multi-Casualty Incidents (MCI):

- Skills needed by the military and civilian structures to improve their coordination in the event of disasters with high casualties and destruction;
- Knowledge of the procedures, principles and means of synchronizing activities in emergency situations, and interaction between military structures and other emergency services, fire, military, police, etc.

Course objectives:

- To create a centralized improvement of the understanding and use of common procedures and training programs for response in Joint Emergency Actions, based on experiences and lessons learned, and covers the emergency spectrum.
- Through the course will be presented the integrated methodology for joint training of current and future military and civilian specialists from the medical services, fire protection services and departments, police and local authorities. This will build a joint educational space, community and a common capacity to interact in emergency planning, preparation and response.
- To put into practice a manual/instruction, interaction procedures and standards for joint training in joint planning and conducting and better coordination of emergency response.
- To improve the joint multinational civil-military training of various representatives engaged in actions in the defeat zone and emergency situations. This will help them use joint civil-military capabilities to perform activities at various cross-border MCIs.
- To build knowledge, skills and competencies for civil-military interaction and common capabilities for civil-military cooperation among representatives of various institutions in the EU countries.

Main focus

Training of specialists from various fields of first response for understanding of possibilities for interaction in emergencies, resulting from natural disasters with mass casualties and destruction.

Target audience

Leaders and specialists from Armed Forces CIMIC teams, Civil Protection, medical services, fire departments, recovery specialists, police and local authorities, police officers at tactical level, representatives of international organizations (IOs), government organizations (GOs) and non-governmental organizations (NGOs), the private sector, agencies and departments and volunteers.

Prerequisites

Recommended advance preparation and Language Proficiency:

Desirable English Level: Minimum Requirement 2222 (Compliant with NATO STANAG 6001);

Research and study, the following documents and training materials:

- Allied Joint Doctrine for the Military Contribution to Humanitarian Assistance;
- Handbook of CIMIC specialists;
- Joint CIMIC Manual;
- Joint Tactics, Technics and Procedures (TTPs).

Training methodology

For training in the course, the following methodology should be followed:

1. The course should develop the knowledge and skills of the trainees in matters related to the foundations of CIMIC and the practical-applied aspects of the planning and management of activities in Emergency Situations, crises and disasters of any nature.
2. The trainees must become familiar with the main approaches and ways of building capabilities for civil-military interaction in emergencies. They study the issues of planning and execution of the civil-military activities and joint actions in emergencies, the development coordination and implementation of activities, mechanisms and approaches for implementing interaction between the force structures and the civilian participants in the emergency zone.
3. The trainees acquire mandatory knowledge, respectively sufficient abilities and skills at a practical-applied level, regarding the main guidelines, mechanisms and approaches for organizing civil-military interaction activities and synchronizing efforts between all structures, forces and resources in conditions of various emergencies.

Competencies level

The trainees should have competencies in the fields of civil-military activities applied in emergencies.

1. Areas of application of acquired knowledge and skills

Training is required for all military and civilian personnel who prepare for appointment at positions in joint multinational emergency response teams. After a successful completion of the course, all trainees will have improved their personal communication skills and will be able to conduct activities related to the CIMIC and Civil Protection. After

completing the training, the acquired knowledge and skills can be applied in the performance of routine duties.

2. After completing the course, trainees should know the essence, goals, tasks and opportunities for interaction; the functional and legal aspects for carrying out the joint activities; the essence of the guiding documents for organizing CIMIC activities in joint multinational actions.
3. After completing the training course, trainees must be able to apply the basic principles and policies of CIMIC and civil protection; to make quickly decisions in accordance with joint standards and procedures in conditions of time and resource deficit; to act flexibly and adaptively, taking calculated and justified risk; to work successfully in multinational teams; to communicate effectively ideas, views (written and verbal) and to motivate teams to support the chosen course of action when conducting joint civil-military activities.

Requirements

- For trainees - educational qualification - not lower than "Bachelor"; specialist or higher.
- Relevance of the course - the course should be updated in 5 years;
- Validity of the acquired qualification: five years.
- The training ends with an exam.
- Duration - 3 days (810 minutes).
- Location: Physical presence and/or online platforms.

Calculation of hours with full employment

Name of the course	Auditory employment				Extracurricular employment		
	Horarium	Lectures	Exercises etc.	Exam	Work with literary sources	Self-preparation	Exam Preparation
JOINT MULTINATIONAL CIMIC COURSE	18	11	7	2	10	6	2

Content

No.	Kind	Duration	Topics	Place	Teacher
1.	L	2	Nature, principles, functions, goals and tasks of Civil-Military Cooperation.	Class	
2.	L	2	Legal and other aspects in Joint Civil-Military Activities. Organization of Joint Multinational and Interagency Actions.	Class	
3.	D	1	Aspects of Joint Multinational and Interagency Actions	Class	
4.	L	1	Training methodology for application of procedures and steps for Civil-Military Interaction in emergency situations	Class	
5.	L	2	Procedures for Civil-Military Interaction and Civil-Military Cooperation in Emergency Situations	Class	
6.	L	2	Procedures for planning and execution of steps for Interaction and Cooperation in Emergency Situations	Class	
7.	L	2	Development of CIMIC and joint assessments in the emergency area	Class	
8.	D	2	Procedures and standards for training and civil-military actions in the emergency area.	Class	
9.	SP	2	Self-preparation	Class	
10.	E	2	Test	Class	
		18			

*Note: L – lecture; D - Discussion; E – Exam; SP – Self-Preparation

Sources of Information

1. Handbook of CIMIC specialists.
2. Doctrine for planning operations.
3. Allied Joint Doctrine for Civil-Military Cooperation, AJP-3.19, 2018.
4. Joint CIMIC Manual.
5. Joint TTPs.
6. Allied Joint Doctrine for the Military Contribution to Humanitarian Assistance.

Feedback Questionnaire

The aim of the survey is to find out to what extent the course organisation has been created, the usefulness of the knowledge gained and the content of the materials and the satisfaction and expectations. At the end of the survey, trainees can submit their recommendations for the course.

1. To what extent does the content of the learning materials in the course correspond to your expectations? Please specify mandatory your torment:

I can't judge	Does not match	There are inconsistencies	It pretty much matches	Corresponds completely
1	2	3	4	5

2. How do you rate the following elements in the course?

Criterion	It's missing	Low	Average	Rather high	Very high
2.1. Relevance of knowledge	1	2	3	4	5
2. 2. Logical connection between individual parts	1	2	3	4	5
2.3. Practical orientation	1	2	3	4	5

3. Level of carrying out of:

Criterion	Weak	Average	Good	Very good	Excellent
Teaching methodology	1	2	3	4	5
Visualization of learning content	1	2	3	4	5
Duration of the course	1	2	3	4	5
Organization of the course	1	2	3	4	5

4. Please indicate your personal opinion which lectures and discussions were useful and why?

.....

5. In your opinion, are you able to apply the presented materials and knowledge in your direct work?

Yes	No
1	2

6. Would you personally recommend your colleagues to take part in this course?

Yes	No
1	2

7. Please give your overall rating for the course:

Weak - 2	Satisfactory – 3	Good - 4	Very good - 5	Excellent - 6
The course is ineffective and does not achieve its goal	The course is not well organized and takes place with gaps	The course is organized and takes place with some gaps	The course is very well organized and provides good training	The course is perfectly organized and provides excellent opportunities and prospects for realization

8. Please give your recommendations and opinions to improve the course

.....

15. Annex D – Evaluation of Exercises for First Responders based on the CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA) “Evaluation of Exercises – Implementation Guidelines”

One of the most important aspects of first responders’ training is the conduct of exercises, through which a variety of aspects can be examined, such as the operational capabilities of a first response organization and of its members, the level of interoperability between different agencies in case of high impact emergencies and the operational value of a new technological solution or procedure among others. Through training exercises, practitioners can increase the level of both preparedness and response to disasters and crises.

Exercises, as an essential tool for training, can be conducted at different levels, from the strategic down to the tactical level, and their objectives may vary from the assessment of first responders’ capabilities in responding to specific simulated situations to the assessment of new tools or even operational procedures and the level of integration of these solutions in operational plans and protocols.

One of the most important elements of the exercises is the evaluation performed. Evaluation covers the entire lifecycle of an exercise, from the initial stage of the exercise planning, through the conduct of the exercise with the data collection and up until the final stage, which includes the data analysis, review and the suggestion of steps for future improvement. Evaluation aims to identify if and to what extent the pre-defined objectives were addressed, these being quantifiable or qualitative, it investigates the performance of the players within different operational capabilities, it allows the identification of strengths and weaknesses of the execution of the exercise, it permits the validation of the performance of a solution against design and expectations and in overall reveals areas for improvement at different dimensions. As a result, the need for the inclusion of a guideline for the evaluation of exercises of every scope, to the training kit proposed by the VALKYRIES project, is deemed essential. To this direction, the CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA) “*Evaluation of exercises – Implementation Guidelines*”, that is being developed under the framework of the H2020 STRATEGY project, officially liaised with VALKYRIES, is proposed. The CWA is currently at the stage of public consultation

This CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA) provides the basic guidelines on the creation of an evaluation scheme for exercises for crisis/disaster management, including exercises aiming to the validation of solutions by practitioners in the context of realistic situations and operational environment (trials). It includes guidance for data collection mainly via the Participant Feedback Form and the Evaluators’ Form and it provides assistance on the eventual data analysis, as part of the evaluation process. A structured and concise form for the after-action and evaluation documentation is also proposed, being recognized as necessary for reporting and filing purposes for future reference and consultation.

Indicative criteria and fields for the evaluation of the exercise conduct, the evaluation of the participants’ performance and for the validation, by the end users, of solutions, based on the CWA, are provided herein.

Criteria to be considered for the evaluation of the exercise conduct:

- Administrative context of the exercise;
- Informative material, used prior to and during the exercise;

-
- Exercise planning meetings;
 - Exercise methodology and structure against exercise objectives;
 - The scenario of the exercise;
 - Exercise coordination and management;
 - Time management and limitations;
 - Availability of resources;
 - Communication means and plan;
 - Logistics;
 - Evaluation of equipment used during the exercise;
 - Exercise structure, procedures and execution compared to the planned objectives;
 - Assessment of the exercise set-up against reality;
 - Accountability;
 - Overall level of satisfaction from the conduct of the exercise;
 - Drawbacks and negative points during the conduct;
 - Ethical and legal aspects;
 - Safety and security measures in place;
 - Strength and weaknesses;
 - Improvements and suggestions
 - General comments.

Criteria to be considered for the evaluation of the players' performance

- Overall rating of the performance of the participating crisis/disaster management group/staff;
against exercise scope and objectives;
- Cooperation and communication (within the organization, across participating organizations and communication with external parties may be also assessed) and possible coordination problems;
- Decision making;
- Information flow;
- Response following the plans and deviations from foreseen plans and guidelines;
- To what extent guidelines or standards referenced are applied;
- Players' creativity and capability in solving emerging problems;
- Players' realistic performance and decision-making;
- Players' physiological and psychosocial aspects;

-
- Constraints set by the available equipment and resources in the success of the participants' efforts;
 - Effectiveness of infrastructure and systems in place, employed as operational tools of the players and their organizations;
 - Effectiveness of the procedures and protocols and relevance to the functions/operations tested Roles and responsibilities;
 - Technical skills tested/trained (e.g., to use a certain ICT-tool);
 - Organizational procedures tested/trained;
 - Impact to capacity building of players (awareness, understanding, decisions taken, level of preparedness) – experience and knowledge gained;
 - Level of player's involvement (possible gaps, overlaps or overwhelming);
 - Interoperability of the different modules and teams deployed for the exercise;
 - Overall level of satisfaction about exercise effectiveness on upgrade of emergency response activities;
 - Comparison of expected outcomes and specific exercise objectives with actual outcomes;
 - Recommendations for corrective actions for capacity upgrade;
 - Recommendations for revision or development of policies, plans, procedures.

Criteria to be considered for the validation of solutions by the end users

According to the under-development CWA, a solution is validated against its usability for the end user. Usability is examined under three main aspects i.e., effectiveness, efficiency and end users' satisfaction. The effectiveness of a solution is validated against the comprehension of the objectives of the system and the level of accomplishment of these objectives. Efficiency includes criteria e.g., time, required resources and ultimate level of accomplishment, using the tested solution, of the pre-defined objectives of the exercise. Finally, end users' satisfaction can be assessed through the following criteria:

- Intended frequency of use;
- Complexity of the solution;
- Ease and pleasure of use, thus exploring structural simplicity, aesthetic and functional aspects of its interface and intuitiveness;
- Need of technical or scientific support for the solutions implementation;
- Level of integration of the functions/procedures in the solution (where applicable)
- Possible inconsistencies;
- Ease of learning to use or follow;
- Overall experience of use (whether it is cumbersome);
- Confidence in use;
- Need for background knowledge.